

Effect of Poverty and Access to Healthcare: A Case Study of Tafawa Balewa Local Government Area, Bauchi State

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Background: Poverty remains a major determinant of health and healthcare utilization in low-resource settings. This study examined the effect of poverty on access to healthcare services in Tafawa Balewa Local Government Area (LGA) of Bauchi State, Nigeria.

Methods: A cross-sectional survey of 324 households was conducted using a structured questionnaire. A multistage sampling technique was employed to select respondents. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics with SPSS version 25, and statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: The findings revealed that 289 respondents (89.2%) identified the high cost of healthcare as the primary barrier to access, followed by inadequate health infrastructure (82.4%). Although healthcare facilities were located within reasonable distance for many residents, shortages of staff, essential medicines, and unaffordable service costs significantly limited utilization. Poverty was strongly associated with delayed treatment-seeking, higher prevalence of preventable diseases, child malnutrition, and increased maternal and child mortality.

Conclusion: Poverty significantly restricts access to healthcare in Tafawa Balewa LGA. Addressing financial and infrastructural barriers through targeted social protection and health system strengthening is essential for improving health outcomes.

Keywords: Poverty; Healthcare access; Health inequality; Socioeconomic factors; Rural health; Tafawa Balewa LGA; Bauchi State; Nigeria

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background of the Study

Poverty remains a significant challenge in many developing countries, including Nigeria, where economic instability, inadequate infrastructure, and limited access to education continue to undermine living standards and health outcomes (Yauri et al., 2024). Poverty is a multidimensional phenomenon characterized not only by insufficient income but also by limited access to essential services such as healthcare (Adedeji, 2023). Globally, poverty perpetuates a vicious cycle in which poor health reduces productivity and income, thereby reinforcing deprivation (Howden-Chapman et al., 2023).

In Bauchi State, healthcare access is constrained by underfunded facilities, shortages of skilled health personnel, poor infrastructure, and high out-of-pocket health expenditures. These challenges are particularly pronounced in Tafawa Balewa LGA, a predominantly agrarian area where most households rely on subsistence farming and petty trading. Understanding how poverty affects healthcare access in this context is critical for designing effective, locally responsive interventions.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Residents of Tafawa Balewa LGA face numerous barriers to accessing healthcare, largely driven by poverty. High medical costs, inadequate healthcare infrastructure, poor availability of essential medicines, and socio-cultural factors continue to limit healthcare utilization. Recent reports highlight persistent difficulties faced by residents in obtaining affordable and quality healthcare services in Bauchi State (Punch Newspaper, 2024). These barriers contribute to delayed treatment-seeking, preventable diseases, and avoidable morbidity and mortality.

1.3 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The main aim of this study is to examine the effect of poverty on access to healthcare services in Tafawa Balewa LGA.

The specific objectives are to:

1. Assess the socio-economic status of households in Tafawa Balewa LGA.
2. Identify major barriers limiting access to healthcare services.
3. Examine the impact of poverty on health outcomes.
4. Recommend strategies to improve healthcare access in the study area.

1.4 Research Questions

- What is the socio-economic profile of households in Tafawa Balewa LGA?
- What barriers do residents face in accessing healthcare services?
- How does poverty influence health outcomes in the community?

1.5 Significance of the Study

The findings of this study provide evidence-based insights for policymakers, healthcare planners, and development partners. The study will support the design of targeted poverty alleviation and healthcare interventions aimed at reducing health inequalities in Bauchi State and similar low-resource settings.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Theoretical Framework

This study is guided by the Functionalist Theory, which links economic inequality to unequal access to social services, and the Individual Attributes Theory, which emphasizes the role of personal and household socio-economic characteristics in shaping health outcomes and healthcare utilization.

2.2 Poverty and Health

Poverty limits access to basic necessities such as adequate nutrition, clean water, sanitation, and healthcare, thereby increasing vulnerability to disease. Poor households are more likely to delay seeking care and experience catastrophic health expenditures, which further deepen poverty (Healthwise Nigeria, 2023).

2.3 Current Levels of Poverty and Healthcare Access

According to Chuma *et al.* (2012), high levels of poverty in developing countries are closely associated with poor access to healthcare and financial hardship due to out-of-pocket payments. Economic shocks, political instability, and public health emergencies such as COVID-19 have further worsened poverty and healthcare access in sub-Saharan Africa (Bhattacharya & Bose, 2023).

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Study Area

The study was conducted in Tafawa Balewa Local Government Area of Bauchi State. The area is semi-urban with a population largely engaged in agriculture and petty trading and faces challenges related to inadequate healthcare facilities and infrastructure.

3.2 Study Design and Population

A descriptive cross-sectional study design was adopted. The study population comprised households in Tafawa Balewa LGA, with an estimated population of 395,200 as of 2022.

3.3 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling technique was employed. In the first stage, wards were selected using simple random sampling. In the second stage, communities were randomly selected from each ward. In the final stage, households were selected systematically. The sample size of 324 households was determined using Cochran's formula and adjusted for a 10% non-response rate.

3.4 Data Collection

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire administered by trained research assistants. The questionnaire was pretested in a neighboring community to ensure clarity, validity, and reliability. An adequate response rate was achieved.

3.5 Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize variables, while chi-square

tests were employed to assess associations between socio-economic variables, healthcare access, and health outcomes. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

3.6 Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Bauchi State University Research Ethics Committee. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained.

4.0 Results and Discussion

The findings reveal widespread poverty among households in Tafawa Balewa LGA, characterized by low income, lack of savings, and reliance on subsistence livelihoods. Financial barriers were identified as the most significant constraint to healthcare access, with nearly 90% of respondents indicating that high medical costs prevent utilization of services. This finding corroborates previous studies that report catastrophic healthcare spending among poor households (Chuma & Maina, 2012; Yauri et al., 2024).

Although healthcare facilities were generally within reasonable distance, shortages of essential medicines, inadequate staffing, and poor infrastructure significantly limited effective access. Poverty was also found to contribute to delayed treatment-seeking, increased prevalence of preventable diseases, child malnutrition, and higher maternal and child mortality. These findings are consistent with broader evidence from sub-Saharan Africa linking poverty to poor health outcomes and inequitable healthcare access (Amponsah et al., 2023).

5.0 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that poverty is a major determinant of access to healthcare in Tafawa Balewa LGA. With 89.2% of respondents identifying cost as a prohibitive barrier, financial hardship remains the most critical obstacle to healthcare utilization. Addressing poverty-related barriers is essential for improving health outcomes and reducing health inequalities in the study area.

6.0 Recommendations

- Government should subsidize healthcare services for low-income households.
- Community-based and social health insurance schemes should be strengthened to reduce out-of-pocket payments.
- Healthcare infrastructure, staffing, and drug supply should be expanded, particularly in rural communities.
- Short-term interventions should focus on financial protection, while long-term strategies should prioritize poverty reduction through livelihood support, education, and social protection programs.
- Monitoring and evaluation mechanisms should be integrated into all interventions.

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